

Phytochemical Investigation on Flowers of *Gliricidia sepium**

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GLIRICIDIA sepium (Syn. *G. maculata*) sometimes known as Madre de cacao (South America) or Kakawate (Philippines) is a fast growing, leguminous, medium sized, thornless tree which can substitute for *Leucaena leucocephala* as a source of fodder, fuelwood and green manure, in hedges and living fences, and as a shade tree in tea, coffee and cocoa plantations¹.

Coumarin, *o*-coumaric acid, melilotic acid and rhamnogalactoside of kaempferol have been reported in the leaves by earlier workers^{2,3}, while the flowers contained only quercetin-3-glucoside⁴. Thus it was thought worthwhile to carry out the detailed chemical analysis of the flowers.

Experimental

The air dry powdered flowers (500 g) were extracted with hot petroleum ether and alcohol, respectively.

Petroleum ether extract showed the presence of waxy material. The alcohol extract was chromatographed over silica gel and elution with solvents of increasing polarity gave four compounds A–D. Compounds A to D were characterised by uv, acetate nmr, permethylation studies and direct comparison with respective authentic samples (co-tlc, m.m.p. and superimposable ir).

Compound A (200 mg), yellow needles, m.p. 178°, was identified as kaempferol-3-glucoside⁵ (astragalin).

The structure of compound B (150 mg), pale yellow needles, m.p. 260°, was found to be kaempferol-3-galactoside⁶ (trifolin). Compound C (5 g), yellow needles, m.p. 196°, $[\alpha]_D - 121^\circ$ (in MeOH), was characterised as kaempferol-3-robinobioside-7-rhamnoside⁷ (robinin). Compound D (10 g), colourless prisms, m.p. 183° $[\alpha]_D + 67^\circ$ (in water), was identified as sucrose.

Conclusion: This is the first report of the occurrence of these compounds in the *Gliricidia sepium* flowers. The flowers can be utilised for the extraction of robinin which occurs in them in 1% yield.

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A New Method for Determination of Sulphites in Polluted Waters

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SULPHITES are commonly found in waste water from pulp and paper mills, in boiler and boiler feed water, and also in cooling process and distribution water system at cold water temperature¹. Sulphite reduces the dissolved oxygen content and COD of water².

Most of the methods including the standard method reported for determination and detection of sulphites in water and waste water are based on iodometric titrations^{1,3,4}, which are subjected to interference from organic matter and other reduced compounds⁵ and are less sensitive. Very few colorimetric methods⁶ are reported for determination of sulphites. Decolourisation of trimethylphenyl dyes by the sulphite solution forms a basis of its analysis colorimetrically⁵.

In this communication a sensitive and selective method for determination of sulphite in water is reported. The method is based upon the liberation of sulphur dioxide from acidified sulphite solution and its absorption in aqueous solution of malonyldihydroxamic acid (MDHA) and is then determined spectrophotometrically using *p*-aminoazobenzene and formaldehyde following the method of Kniseley and Throop⁷. This reagent system has already been reported for the determination of sulphur dioxide in air⁸. The reported method is highly sensitive and selective for sulphites in water, waste and river water. Most of the common pollutants present in water such as nitrate, nitrite, sulphate, fluoride, phosphate, ammonia and metallic cations do not interfere.

Experimental

Apparatus: An ECIL GS 865 spectrophotometer and Carl Zeiss Spekol with 1 cm matched glass cells were used for spectrophotometric measurements.

Reagents : Malonyldihydroxamic acid (MDHA)^o (0.01 M) was prepared by adding dimethylmalonate (16 g) to the ammoniacal solution of 14 g of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (14 g) with vigorous shaking at 0° and the resulting white ppt was filtered and recrystallised twice with demineralised water.

A 0.02% solution of recrystallised *p*-aminoazobenzene was prepared in 20% ethanol. Formaldehyde solution (0.2%) was prepared by diluting 0.5 ml of 38-40% formaldehyde to 100 ml with demineralised water. A stock solution of sulphite was prepared by dissolving predried sodium sulphite (2 g) in demineralised water (250 ml) containing 0.32 to 0.40 mg ml⁻¹ sulphur dioxide and the solution was standardised iodometrically. Working standards were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock in 0.01 M MDHA.

A.R. grade chemicals were used and demineralised deaerated water was used for preparing the solutions.

Pre-treatment of sample : Sample solutions containing nitrite and sulphides interfere with the method. Nitrite was removed by adding a few drops of sulphamic acid^o to the sample solution and a few drops of lead acetate added to remove interference of sulphide, if necessary.

Procedure : Sulphur dioxide was generated quantitatively from the acidified solution of sulphites and liberated sulphur dioxide was absorbed in 0.01M MDHA. Two midget impingers (35 ml capacity) each containing 10 ml of 0.01 MDHA as absorbing solution were connected in a series and then to a rotameter and vacuum pump. 15 ml of 2M hydrochloric acid was added dropwise from a microburette into a chamber containing the pre-treated sample solution. 38.2 dm³ purified air was passed through the solution at a rate of 0.75 dm³ min⁻¹. The liberated sulphur dioxide was absorbed in 0.01M MDHA solution. After sampling, an aliquot (depending upon the concentration of sulphur dioxide) was transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask. To this 1 ml of *p*-aminoazobenzene was added and the acidity was adjusted to 0.02-0.05M with hydrochloric acid. Then 1 ml of formaldehyde followed by 1 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid were added and made upto the mark with demineralised and deaerated water. The absorbance of the pink coloured solution was measured after 20 min at 505 nm using distilled water as reference. Reagent blank was prepared similarly.

Calibration graph was prepared by taking an aliquot of sulphite solution in 0.01M MDHA containing 2.5 to 25 µg of SO₂/25 ml.

Results and Discussion

The stability and absorbing efficiency of sulphur dioxide in MDHA were studied. It was found that generation of sulphur dioxide was quantitative and the data are reproducible and accurate.

Effect of variables on colour development : The maximum colour intensity was obtained when acidity was adjusted to 0.1-0.8 M with hydrochloric acid, after the addition of *p*-aminoazobenzene and formaldehyde, respectively to the solution of MDHA containing absorbed sulphur dioxide. 15 min were required for full colour development and the product was stable upto 12 h at room temperature.

Beer's law and reproducibility : The absorbance was measured at λ_{max} 505 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the range of 2.5 to 25 µg per 25 ml of sulphur dioxide in 0.01M MDHA. The reproducibility of the method was studied by taking replicate analysis of the standard sulphite solution. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be 0.0034 and 0.89%, respectively.

Effect of diverse species : The effect of copollutants present in water were studied. For this purpose, known amount of diverse ions were added to the standard solution of sulphites. From this solution, sulphur dioxide was generated and analysed by the above reported procedure. Quantitatively, nitrite and sulphide do not interfere upto the range of 0.2 and 0.5 ppm, respectively. Tolerance limit of the effects of diverse species are as follows: Fe^{II}, Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}, Cr^{II}, Al^{III}, Co^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Bi^{III}, Hg^{II}, SO₄²⁻, CO₃²⁻, Cl⁻, F⁻ and PO₄²⁻, 1000 ppm and above; and NO₂⁻ and H₂S interfere. Tolerance limit is the amount of interferent that cause an error of ± 2% or less.

Application of the method for analysis of polluted and paper pulp waste water : Samples of polluted river water were taken and analysed by the above procedure after the pre-treatment of the sample. Since the amount of sulphites in the water was negligible, known amount of sulphite was added to it and the recovery was checked by the reported method. The data is given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RECOVERY OF SULPHITES FROM POLLUTED WATER

Flow rate=0.75 dm ³ min ⁻¹ Volume of air sampled=88.2 dm ³	
Amount of SO ₂ added in polluted water µg	Amount of SO ₂ found µg
15.00	14.98 ± 0.017
30.00	29.95 ± 0.032
45.00	44.97 ± 0.031
60.00	59.98 ± 0.020
75.00	74.96 ± 0.029
90.00	89.99 ± 0.011
100.00	99.96 ± 0.040

It was found that effluents of the paper pulp industry which were added to the river containing varying amounts of sulphites range from 100 to 2000 ppm.

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Thin Layer Chromatography of Azine and Oxazine Dyes†

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PIETSCH and Meyer¹ employed tlc for the analysis of dyes, while Dobres and Moats² used ascending tlc for the analysis of some common dyes, but the tlc of azine and oxazine dyes has not been studied so far. We have, therefore, undertaken the present study which involves a simple and rapid method for the separation of impurities in eight azine dyes and six oxazine dyes by the ascending tlc technique.

Experimental

The azine dyes investigated are, Neutral Violet (NV), Neutral Red (NR), Azocarmine G (ACG), Azocarmine B (ACB), Wool Fast Blue GL (WFBGL), Magdala Red (MR), Indulin Water Soluble (IWS), and Nigrosin (NG) (C. I. nos. 50030, 50040, 50085, 50090, 50320, 50375, 50405 and 50420, respectively), and the oxazine dyes are, Capri Blue (CB), Solochrome Prune AS (SPAS), Gallamine Blue (GB), Celestine Blue (CLB), Meldola's Blue (MB), and Nile Blue (NB) (C.I. nos. 51015, 51040, 51045, 51050, 51175 and 51180, respectively). The samples NV, NR, ACG, CB, SPAS, GB, CLB and MB were of George T. Gurr; ACB, MR and IWS of Edward Gurr; NG and NB of Fluka; and WFBGL of Bayer.

† The work on azine dyes presented at the 69th. session of the Indian Science Congress, Mysore, January 3-7, 1982, and that on oxazine dyes at the 53rd. session of the National Academy of Sciences (India), Goa, October 27-29, 1983.

The solvents employed for developing the chromatograms were of reagent grade quality.

Glass plates of size 75 μ were coated (250 μ thickness) with silica gel (particle size : 75 μ , Acme Synthetic Chemicals), prepared by the addition of 30 g of the gel to 60 ml of water and shaking thoroughly. The plates were activated by heating in an oven at 120° for 30 min. Methanolic or ethanolic solutions (0.1%) of the dyes were used for spotting and the following solvent systems were used for developing the chromatograms (A to D for the azine dyes, and E to L for the oxazine dyes): (A) benzene-chloroform-ethanol (5 : 3 : 3), (B) benzene-isobutanol-isopropanol-acetic acid-water (8 : 4 : 4 : 3 : 1), (C) chloroform-ethyl acetate-acetic acid-water (4 : 4 : 4 : 1), (D) chloroform-n-propanol-isopropanol (10 : 7 : 3), (E) chloroform-isopropanol-ethanol-acetic acid (10 : 6 : 4 : 1), (F) chloroform-isopropanol-ethanol (5 : 3 : 2), (G) chloroform-n-butanol-ethanol (5 : 4 : 2), (H) methanol-acetic acid (1 : 1), (I) glacial acetic acid, (J) benzene-methanol-acetic acid (13 : 5 : 2), (K) acetone-acetic acid (1 : 1), and (L) acetic acid-benzene-methanol (5 : 3 : 2).

2 to 3 μ l of the dye sample was spotted on the activated silica gel plates and developed with suitable solvent systems. After development, the chromatograms were air-dried and the R_f values determined for the visible spots. Thereafter, the chromatograms were sprayed with 5% methanolic sulphuric acid to detect any further impurities present.

Results and Discussion

Azine dyes : Of the eight azine dyes studied, six dyes, viz. NV, NR, ACG, ACB, WFBGL and NR gave good separations. IWS separated to some extent, but NG could not be separated. Use of solvent systems containing a single solvent resulted in poor separations. Acidic solvent systems have, however, been found to be satisfactory. Solvent systems containing strong alkalis, like NaOH, yielded poor resolution and tailing-off of many compounds. Incorporation of varying amounts of ammonia in the above systems has not yielded satisfactory separation of the compounds, whereas, incorporation of acetic acid resulted in better separations. Incorporation of a small amount (0.5% v/v) of HCl in solvent system (A) produced excellent resolution.

NR separated as five spots with R_f values, 0.82 (intense pink, major dye), 0.77 (light pink), 0.88 (light orange-yellow), 0.20 (light pinkish violet), and 0 (very light yellow). NV gave somewhat similar results with slight changes in R_f values and an additional red spot of very light intensity with R_f value 0.58. WFBGL has been observed as a single spot in all the solvent systems studied which indicates that the dye is highly pure. ACG separated as four spots with R_f values, 0.25 (intense orange-red, major dye), 0.17 (light red), 0.10 (light red), and 0.9